

of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde (3) with benzoylacetonitrile in the presence of piperidine⁹. Cyclisation of 1 with concentrated sulphuric acid resulted in the formation of 6*H*-indeno[1,2-*b*] [1,8]naphthyridin-6-one (2) in good yield. The formation of the same compound (2) was confirmed by the unambiguous synthesis involving the Friedlander's condensation of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde (3) with indane-1,3-dione (4), in the presence of ethanol containing a catalytic amount of piperidine. The compounds obtained by the two methods were identical in all respects (m.p., m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir).

The structure assignment of 2 was based on elemental analysis and spectral (ir, mass and pmr) data. Formation of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone and a strong band at 1720 cm^{-1} in its ir spectrum indicated the presence of carbonyl group. The spectrum also exhibited bands at 1600, 1460, 1400, 1380, 1220, 1190, 1090, 980, 950, 930, 880, 780 and 730 cm^{-1} . In the mass spectra, the molecular ion peak was observed at m/z 232 which corresponds to the molecular formula $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}$. The pmr spectrum was also in agreement with the proposed structure.

Experimental

The homogeneity and purity of the compounds were tested by tlc. Ir spectrum (nujol) was recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 283 spectrophotometer, pmr spectrum (CDCl_3) on a 100 MHz Varian spectrometer using TMS as internal reference, and mass spectrum on a Varian MAT CH-7 instrument.

3-Cyano-2-phenyl-1,8-naphthyridine: It was prepared by the condensation of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde (3) with benzoylacetonitrile by the method of Hawes and Wibberley⁹ in 80% yield, m.p. 223 (lit. 224–25°).

2-Phenyl-1,8-naphthyridine-3-carboxylic acid (1): A solution of potassium hydroxide (2 g) in water (2 ml) was added to a solution of 3-cyano-2-phenyl-1,8-naphthyridine (1 g) in ethanol (20 ml) and the solution was heated under reflux for 14 h. The ethanol was evaporated on a steam-bath, then water (20 ml) added, and the solution acidified with glacial

acetic acid to yield the acid (70%), m.p. 260° (lit.⁹ 259–60).

6*H*-Indeno[1,2-*b*] [1,8]naphthyridin-6-one (2): *Method-A:* Compound 1 (1 g) and concentrated sulphuric acid (10 ml) were heated on a water-bath for 3 h. The solution was cooled and poured onto crushed ice and basified with ammonia solution. The separated solid was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol, (50%), m.p. 278° (Found: C, 77.49; H, 3.41; N, 12.01. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}$ requires: C, 77.85; H, 3.44; N, 12.06%); 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. > 300° (Found: C, 61.08; H, 2.89; N, 20.32. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_6\text{O}_4$ requires: C, 61.16; H, 2.91; N, 20.38%). *Method-B:* A mixture of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde (3; 0.1 mol) and indene-1,3-dione (4; 0.1 mol) was refluxed in ethanol (30 ml) in the presence of a catalytic amount of piperidine for 0.5 h. The reaction mixture was cooled, and the separated solid filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. E. V. Sundaram, Head, Department of Chemistry and Dean, Faculty of Science, Kakatiya University, Warangal, for facilities, and to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

References

1. K. MOGILAIAN, K. RAGHAVA RAJU and B. SREENIVASULU, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1981, 20, 821.
2. K. MOGILAIAN and B. SREENIVASULU, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1982, 21, 682.
3. K. V. REDDY, K. MOGILAIAN and B. SREENIVASULU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, 61, 888.
4. K. R. REDDY, K. MOGILAIAN and B. SREENIVASULU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, 63, 984.
5. K. MOGILAIAN and B. SREENIVASULU, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1982, 21, 479.
6. K. MOGILAIAN, K. V. REDDY and B. SREENIVASULU, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1983, 22, 178.
7. K. V. REDDY, K. MOGILAIAN and B. SREENIVASULU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, 63, 443.
8. E. M. HAWES and D. G. WIBBERLEY, *J. Chem. Soc. (C)*, 1967, 1566.

Synthesis of 2,3-Dihydro-5,7-dihydroxy-8-(γ,γ dimethylallyl)-2-(4'-hydroxy-2'-methoxy)phenyl-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one

(MS.) RENU CHOPRA and M. KRISHNAMURTI*

Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi,
Delhi-110 007

Manuscript received 24 November 1986, accepted 6 July 1987

In a recent paper, McCormick *et al.*¹ reported the isolation of 8-C-prenyl-2'-methoxy-5,7,4'-trihydroxyflavanone from *Wyethia glabra*. Its structure was deduced on the basis of spectral evidences. We

report herein the synthesis of a flavanone corresponding to the above structure.

The synthesis of **1** was achieved starting from 2'-hydroxy-4,4',6'-tri(methoxymethoxy)-2-methoxychalcone (**2**), which on prenylation with prenyl bromide in presence of methanolic KOH furnished 2'-hydroxy-4,4',6'-tri(methoxymethoxy)-2-methoxy-3'-(γ,γ -dimethylallyl)chalcone (**3**). The chalcone (**2**) was synthesised by condensation of 4,6-di(methoxymethoxy)-2-hydroxyacetophenone² (**4**) with 2-methoxy-4-(methoxymethoxy)benzaldehyde (**5**). Cyclisation of **3** with alcoholic NaOAc afforded **6** which on demethoxymethylation using methanolic HCl afforded the title compound (**1**). The synthetic sample had characteristics similar to those reported for the natural sample. However, a direct comparison could not be made because the sample was not available with the authors who isolated it.

Experimental

Unless stated otherwise, all m.p.s. are uncorrected. UV spectra (MeOH) were recorded on a Shimadzu 260 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu IR-435 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 and also on Jeol FX-200 (200 MHz) FT instruments using tetramethylsilane as internal standard.

2'-Hydroxy-4,4',6'-tri(methoxymethoxy)-2-methoxychalcone (2): 2-Hydroxy-4,6-di(methoxymethoxy)acetophenone (**4**) (4.0 g) and 4-(methoxymethoxy)-2-methoxybenzaldehyde (**5**; 3.8 g) (which was synthesised from β -resorcydehyde by partial methoxymethylation followed by methylation by usual procedures) were taken in ethanol (25 ml). Alcoholic KOH (25 g in 50 ml ethanol) was then slowly added to it with constant stirring maintaining the temperature at 15–20°. The solution was then allowed to stand in the refrigerator for 3 days and the product worked up as usual. The chalcone was purified by column chromatography over silica gel

using petroleum ether—acetone (24 : 1) as eluent. It was crystallised from petroleum ether as fluffy orange yellow crystals (2.8 g), m p 64–5° (Found : C, 60.4; H, 6.1. C₂₂H₂₆O₉ requires : C, 60.8; H, 6.0%); $\lambda_{\max}$ 204, 248, 312 and 374 nm; $\nu_{\max}$ 3100, 1610, 1535, 1495, 1440, 1390, 1340, 1305, 1275, 1210, 1190, 1140, 1100, 1074, 1050, 985, 960 and 910 cm⁻¹; δ 3.48 (9H, s, OCH₂OCH₃), 3.85 (3H, s, OCH₃), 5.13 (2H, s, OCH₂OCH₃), 5.22 (4H, s, 2 × OCH₂OCH₃), 6.22 (2H, d, *J* 3 Hz, H-3' and 5'), 6.55 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz, H- β), 7.3 (1H, s br, H-3), 7.5 (2H, dd, *J* 17 Hz and 1 Hz, H-5 and H-6), 8.02 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz, H- α), 12.8 (1H, s, chelated OH).

2'-Hydroxy-4,4',6'-tri(methoxymethoxy)-2-methoxy-3'-(γ,γ -dimethylallyl)chalcone (3): The above chalcone (**2**; 2.0 g) was added to a well cooled solution of KOH (2.0 g) in absolute methanol (30 ml) and the whole solution was cooled to 0°. Prenyl bromide (3 ml) was then added dropwise with continuous stirring and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 3–4 h. The product after usual work-up was subjected to column chromatography over silica gel. The prenylated chalcone eluted with petroleum ether—acetone (49 : 1) as a dark yellow solid, was crystallised from ethanol, (1.5 g), m.p. 114° (Found : C, 64.2; H, 6.8. C₂₇H₃₄O₉ requires : C, 64.5; H, 6.8%); $\lambda_{\max}$ 204, 224, 306 and 374 nm; $\nu_{\max}$ 3250, 1645, 1600, 1560, 1500, 1420, 1390, 1340, 1240, 1150, 1060, 990, 970 and 910 cm⁻¹; δ 1.72, 1.78 (6H, 2s, C(CH₃)₂), 3.49 (11H, m, 3 × OCH₂OCH₃ and CH₂-CH=), 3.9 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.9 (2H, s, OCH₂OCH₃), 5.26 (5H, m, 2 × OCH₂OCH₃ and CH₂-CH=), 6.6 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, H- β), 6.72 (1H, s, H-5'), 7.6 (3H, m, H-3, 5 and 6), 8.0 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, H- α) and 13.02 (1H, s, chelated OH).

5,7,4'-Tri(methoxymethoxy)-2'-methoxy-8-(γ,γ -dimethylallyl)flavanone (6): To the above prenylated chalcone (**3**; 1.0 g) in ethanol (30 ml), sodium acetate (6.0 g) was added. The mixture was maintained at 60–70° for 3–4 h and then left at room temperature for 4 days. The product which was a mixture of the chalcone and flavanone was subjected to column chromatography over silica gel. The flavanone was obtained as dark yellow liquid on elution with petroleum ether—acetone (45 : 5) (Found : C, 64.2; H, 6.5. C₂₇H₃₄O₉ requires : C, 64.5; H, 6.8%); $\lambda_{\max}$ 205, 238 and 270 nm; $\nu_{\max}$ 1660, 1600, 1580, 1520, 1465, 1380, 1340, 1270, 1240, 1160, 1040, 980, 920 and 820 cm⁻¹; δ 1.75, 1.79 (6H, 2s, C(CH₃)₂), 2.79–2.87 (2H, m, H-3), 3.48 (11H, m, 3 × OCH₂OCH₃ and CH₂-CH=), 3.79 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.62 (1H, s, CH₂-CH=), 5.18 (6H, d, OCH₂OCH₃), 5.61 (1H, d, H-2), 6.3 (1H, s, H-6), 6.60, 6.67 (1H each, 2dd, H-3' and 5') and 7.46 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, H-6').

5,7,4'-Trihydroxy-2'-methoxy-8-(γ,γ -dimethylallyl)flavanone or (2,3-dihydro-5,7-dihydroxy-8-(γ,γ -dimethylallyl)-2'-(4'-hydroxy-2'-methoxy)phenyl-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one (1): The flavanone (**6**; 100 mg)

was dissolved in methanol (5 ml), 3*N* hydrochloric acid (5 ml) added and the contents were boiled for 5–10 min. Ice-cold water was then added and the solution extracted with ether. The organic layer was washed with water, dried (Na₂SO₄) and concentrated. The flavanone was obtained as a yellow coloured solid (20 mg) m.p. 148° (Found: C, 67.7; H, 6.6. C₂₁H₁₈O₆ requires: C, 67.4; H, 7.0%); λ_{max} 240 and 285 nm; ν_{max} 3 390, 1 660, 1 610, 1 575, 1 550, 1 500, 1 460, 1 380, 1 290, 1 250, 1 160, 1 040, 980, 920, 810 and 780 cm⁻¹; δ (acetone-d₆) 1.79 (6H, s, C(CH₃)₂), 2.70–2.82 (2H, m, H-3), 3.42 (5H, d, *J* 7 Hz, CH₂-CH= and OCH₃), 4.63 (1H, t, *J* 7 Hz, CH₂-CH=), 5.66 (1H, dd, *J* 12.5 Hz and 3.8 Hz, H-2), 6.85 (2H, s, H-3' and 5'), 7.66 (1H, s, H-2') and 12.47 (1H, s, OH).

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (R.C.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship.

References

1. S. McCORMICK, K. BOBSON and B. BOHM, *Phytochemistry*, 1985, 24, 1614.
2. E. SHERIF, A. ISLAM and M. KRISHNAMURTI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1982, 21, 478.

Synthesis and Antibacterial Activity of Azomethines and Thiazolidinone Derivatives of Benzimidazoles

R. K. SAKSENA* and S. K. SRIVASTAVA

Department of Chemistry, D. A.V. College, (Kanpur University), Kanpur-208 001

Manuscript received 25 September 1985, revised 9 March 1987, accepted 6 July 1987

BENZIMIDAZOLE derivatives exhibit a wide spectrum of biological activities such as antibacterial¹⁻³, insecticidal⁴, fungicidal⁵, virucidal⁶ and antiparasitic^{7,8} activities. Several thiazolidinone derivatives are found to possess diverse biological properties, viz. fungicidal⁹, antibacterial¹⁰, anticonvulsant¹¹ and amoebicidal¹². In continuation of our earlier work on thiazolidinones¹³ possessing heterocyclic moieties, we report here the synthesis and antibacterial activity of some azomethines and thiazolidinone derivatives with benzimidazole moiety in a single molecular framework.

The key intermediate, 2-*N*-(*p*-aminophenyl/diphenyl)aminomethylbenzimidazole (1) was refluxed with different arylaldehydes in absolute ethanol in the presence of acetic acid to get the desired 2-*N*-(*p*-arylidene-aminophenyl/diphenyl)aminomethylbenzimidazoles (2) which undergo cyclocondensation with

mercaptoacetic acid to furnish 2-*p*-(2-aryl-4-oxothiazolin-3-yl) phenyl / diphenylaminomethylbenzimidazole (3). Structure of compounds 2 and 3 were established on the basis of their elemental analyses and ir spectra. Compound 2 gave important bands at 3 280–3 310 (N–H stretch), 1 600–1 625 (C=N azomethines) and 1 360–1 375 cm⁻¹ (pentacyclic ring). Spectra of compound 3 gave peaks at 3 285–3 310 (N–H), 2 905–2 950 (CH₂), 1 630–1 655 (C=O) and 1 250–1 310 cm⁻¹ (C–S–C).

Experimental

Melting points were determined in a sulphuric acid bath in open capillary and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin–Elmer 377 spectrophotometer. Tlc was done on silica gel plates.

2-*N*-(*p*-Aminophenyl)aminomethylbenzimidazole (1): 2-Chloromethylbenzimidazole¹⁴ (0.01 mol) and 1,4-diaminobenzene (0.01 mol) were refluxed in dry benzene for 4 h, and then excess benzene was distilled off. The separated solid was washed with petroleum ether and recrystallised from ethanol, (70%), m.p. 162° (Found: N, 23.48. C₁₄H₁₄N₄ requires: N, 23.52%).

Similarly, 2-*N*-(*p*-aminodiphenyl)aminomethylbenzimidazole (1b) was obtained, m.p. 192° (Found: N, 17.80, C₂₀H₁₈N₄ requires: N, 17.83%).

2-*N*-(*p*-Arylideneaminophenyl/diphenyl)aminomethylbenzimidazole (2): A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol), arylaldehyde (0.01 mol), ethanol (30 ml) and glacial acetic acid (0.5 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. The resulting mixture was cooled and poured over